

D2.1 – Requirements and Prototype Specifications

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Summary sheet

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ACRONYMS

Acronyms are defined in the attached annex.

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Executive summary

Deliverable 2.1 (Requirements and Prototype Specification) provides an overview of the requirements agreed upon by the NEMO consortium for the implementation of all objectives, demonstrators and KPIs.

This report shows the procedure coming from the objectives to the requirements for implementation of the NEMOs demonstrators zBMS and zBMS+ and the cell selection used for the demonstrators.

Partners' Contributions

Partner institution	Sections	Description of the contribution
IAV	All	Drafting the deliverable
All	Annex (GitLab)	Capturing of Requirements
VUB, CSEM	All	Review

1. Introduction

The deliverable 2.1 builds the base for further work in the project NEMO. This work of definition involves all technical partners and is mainly driven by the industrial partners. This deliverable describes the specifications of the various hardware/software solutions, their capabilities, and the set of tests.

This deliverable is dedicated to the analysis of different use scenarios from transport and stationary applications and the detailed description of the use cases that will be considered for testing purposes in WP7. For these use cases, the technical requirements for the model and algorithm developments in WP3/WP4 and the hard- and software developments in WP5/WP6 will be derived. It includes also the selection of the battery cell (chemistry, packaging, etc.) that is going to be used as a reference for testing and prototype development throughout the project.

The detailed technical specifications for the prototype developments are defined here. This includes the hardware specifications for the prototype in WP5 and the software specifications for the operation of the prototype that is developed in WP6, which also encompasses the support of the integration of the models and algorithms from WP3/WP4. The work also includes the exact definition of the KPIs that will be used to verify the conformity of the specifications (e.g., the definition of SoS) and their boundary conditions (e.g., the definition of SoH and dependence on temperature, etc.).

The detailed requirements, derived from objectives 1 to 6, for the demonstrators are elaborated and collected in this deliverable. All dependencies of the requirements are clearly shown. All the requirements for the demonstrators (zBMS and zBMS+) functional and parametric are specified there.

Objectives of D2.1.:

The objective of this deliverable is to define:

- the use cases
- the requirement for hardware and software development
- the specification of the prototype demonstrators
- and the specifications and definition of KPIs

Inputs:

The input for this deliverable has been worked out in several meetings. Each partner has added his input. Derived from these inputs, the specification for the demonstrator has been defined.

Main Results:

The main result of this deliverable is the specification of the demonstrators zBMS and zBMS+. These requirements are the basis for all further work. A further result of this report is the description of the use cases and the derived requirements.

2. Deliverable D2.1

2.1 Objectives and KPI

The NEMO consortium has identified six main project objectives. These objectives are described in the following paragraphs, where firstly the current situation and associated shortcomings (see current state-of-the-art (SoTA)) are summarized, then the suggested approach within NEMO is detailed and how this goes beyond the current SoTA (see NEMO solution). The description is finally completed with an outline of the associated NEMO deliverables (see NEMO outcome) and how the consortium is going to validate the results within the project (see NEMO KPIs).

2.1.1. OBJ1 – Demonstration of improved sensor signal acquisition and increased computational resources for battery management systems

Current SoTA: Current BMS acquire voltage and temperature at the cell level and current on the string level with acquisition rates typically in the 1 to 10 Hz range. Additional sensors as those studied within the Battery2030+ initiative are not yet integrated. Signal acquisition is based on the master-slave concept, where slaves typically acquire 12 to 16 cell voltage and temperature signals; processing is done exclusively on the string master, which also includes current sensing. Computing power on the master is limited and restricted to the usage of simple algorithms like Coulomb counting or simple Kalman filters with up to 2 to 4 state variables.

NEMO solution: Implementation of zBMS concept with the inclusion of cell-level electrochemical impedance spectroscopy as additional sensor input; continuous EIS acquisition in an idle state but also under load, and sensor signal acquisition up to 100 Hz for all other sensor signals; implementation of distributed computation approach and wireless data communication; increased computational resources (through AURIX™ TC4x1) via multi-core processors (up to 6 central processing units (CPUs)) and digital signal processing (DSP) support (via parallel processing unit (So) accelerator for high performance and affordable AI) to allow execution of complex algorithms (fast Fourier transform (FFT), matrix operation, multilayer perceptron, etc.).

NEMO outcome: zBMS+ platform with distributed computing, active balancing, and wireless connectivity.

NEMO KPIs: Hardware performance of zBMS concept as specified in D2.2 and documented in D5.3 and D6.3.

2.1.2. OBJ2 – Validation of improvements stemming from an automatic model update on SoC estimation

Current SotA: State estimators are based on Coulomb counting or use simple battery models (e.g., 2-state Kalman filters) with fixed parameters. Ageing effects are considered via continuous model calibration (e.g., through capacity comparison for full or partial charge/discharge under open circuit voltage (OCV) conditions), which however shows practical limitations and imprecisions caused by temperature dependence and charge/discharge current conditions.

NEMO solution: The local P-ECM and the cloud-based P2D model are updated regularly based on continuous sensor data. For the P-ECM parameter, extraction is performed via distribution of relaxation time (DRT) analysis of the EIS signals, whereas machine learning approaches are used for the P2D model. The state-of-charge (SoC) is determined with the BESTIMATOR™ algorithm framework, which is adapted to host and compare the different physical models.

NEMO outcome: BESTIMATOR™ SoC estimator validated on the zBMS platform for 18 months.

NEMO KPIs: SoC maximum absolute percentage error (MAPE) error performance below 1.0% after 18 months.

2.1.3. OBJ3 – Validation of improved lifetime modelling via advanced SoH and RUL algorithms

Current SotA: Battery lifetime modelling is performed using purely empirical approaches, which consider capacity fade and internal resistance increase.

NEMO solution: Three different ageing models are implemented: a semi-empirical approach based on the coupling of electrochemical P2D and data-driven ageing models, an EIS-driven mechanical swelling model (MSM) that relates ageing to the evolution of local cell pressure variation, and an ageing model that is based on the analysis of the parameter evolution of the P-ECM model. All models are based on periodical parameter updates based on operational measurement data that exploit EIS signals. The models will be applied to determine state-of-health (SoH) estimation and remaining useful life (RUL) prediction.

NEMO outcome: Different ageing models validated on zBMS platform data for 18 months.

NEMO KPIs: SoH MAPE error performance below 1% and RUL MAPE error performance below 3%.

2.1.4. OBJ4 – Demonstration of battery lifetime extension via SoH-balancing at the cell level

Current SotA: Cells of a string in a battery module or pack do age differently according to slight differences in their initial state (manufacturing variations) and local variations of usage conditions (thermal stress, etc.). The weakest cell in a string always determines the

performance of the entire string and nowadays already used passive balancing schemes, which use bypass currents below 1% of the cell capacity rating, are not able to equilibrate SoH over all cells in a string during the entire battery lifetime.

NEMO solution: The precise knowledge of ageing via the cell-level SoH estimators provided by the advanced physics models developed in the project (P2D, P-ECM, MSM, etc.) allows SoH balancing via the active balancing system of the zBMS+ platform. The active balancing concept switches individual cells in and out, where the SoH knowledge of each cell will be used to determine the timing whereas the operational conditions (module voltage level and current draw) will determine the number of cells that will be switched out. This approach allows prolonged rest times for aged cells such that all cells in a string age equally during the entire lifetime.

NEMO outcome: SoH balancing validated on the zBMS+ platform for 12 months based on already cycled cells (we target roughly 24 months of effective cell usage, which should bring us down to 80% remaining capacity).

NEMO KPIs: Module level lifetime extension of 20% at 80% of the remaining capacity.

2.1.5. OBJ5 – Validation of early failure detection via cell pressure and core temperature estimation under load

Current SotA: Battery failures that are not captured via condition monitoring (overvoltage, overcurrent, charging at sub-freezing temperature etc.) are due to design flaws involving microscopic metallic particles, which are rather rare, or stress events like vibration or severe mechanical damage (e.g., penetration)². Cell penetration can be avoided via structural designs, offering mechanical protection, however, the effects caused by parasitic metallic particles or those originating from mechanical alterations are not monitored.

NEMO solution: The observation of the parameter evolution of the EIS-driven MSM provides insight into the evolution of mechanical stress and its intensity whereas the exploitation of EIS for the estimation of the core cell temperature provides the early detection of unusual internal temperature increase, which indicates early failure patterns. Destructive stress test based on mechanical loads (e.g., vibration) and TR generation via external triggers (e.g., incremental increase of local mechanical deformation, heating) will be used to characterize early failure detection based on a single cell zBMS+ unit, where cell switching is used to isolate dangerous cells.

NEMO outcome: Definition of state-of-safety (SoS indicator based on obtained failure characteristics and associated trigger levels).

NEMO KPIs: Cell failure or TR events can be detected with an accuracy of 100% for the defined failure modes and triggers.

2.1.6. OBJ6 – Demonstrating data management performance and providing FAIR data for the research community

Current SotA: BMS data is acquired locally for operation purposes but not stored. Data transmission to cloud services for storage and analysis are not yet common practice or is limited to internal use at original equipment manufacturers (OEM). First commercial analysis tools exist, like e.g., offered by Aviloo3 or Accure4, but are limited to short-term data storage and analysis. Consequently, access to operational data for research and development purposes is rather fragmented and limited.

NEMO solution: All acquired data at the cell and module level from all characterization (WP3 and WP4) and validation experiments (WP7) are consequently stored in the NEMO cloud. Data will be formatted according to the BattINFO5 ontology proposed by the BIG-MAP EC project to make it easily reusable. Suitable data compression will be applied to reduce data transmission and cloud data storage requirements.

NEMO outcome: NEMO measurement data is publicly available on the project website (later in a public repository).

NEMO KPIs: 100% of useful BMS data is available in the cloud, and software performance is documented in D6.3.

2.2 Methodology

Requirements Engineering is getting more and more important since the implementation of the standard ISO26262, and since the systems are getting more and more complex. Without proper requirements engineering a complete verification and validation of complex systems might not be possible.

Several tools for collecting, linking and deriving requirements are available. In the project NEMO the consortium decided to use Sphinx-Needs as tool, which allows to create, manage and analyze requirements, specifications, test case and more inside Sphinx based documentations.

The consortium decided to use Gitlab as version control system to track the changes of requirements and build the report.

The following methodology is used for capturing requirements. Starting from the objectives, the root requirements and user stories are derived. All functional and parametric requirements are defined with relation to the root requirements. As the verification is part of the project goal, the verification requirements are derived as well.

2.3 Report

The final report is provided in the subsequent pages.

3 Deviations

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved in full and as scheduled.

Due to unforeseen circumstances, the initially designated Westart 105 Ah battery cells were unavailable. Consequently, the NEMO consortium made the decision to utilize Westart 75 Ah battery cells as an alternative. As a result, deliverable 2.1 was updated to incorporate the new battery cell specifications.

4 Annexes

The acronyms and glossary can be found in the subsequent pages.

NEMO - Deliverable D2.1

ANNEX

NEMO Consortium

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USER STORIES

A user story explains a function, a feature or a property of the system with only one or two sentences from the customers point of view (who wants what and what for).

All user stories are derived from the objectives.

Battery system *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*

links outgoing: None

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_c6aaf740, NEMO_SYS_cbca87d8, NEMO_SYS_67160af1*

is related to: *NEMO_SYS_46a436ed, NEMO_SYS_4292ca81, NEMO_SYS_e085f55d, NEMO_SYS_8acb6b1c, NEMO_SYS_c4ac9210, NEMO_SYS_1ca63335, NEMO_SYS_39ccd240, NEMO_SYS_4d69ca22, NEMO_SYS_6cb92f5f, NEMO_SYS_9cfc0bfd*

The battery system shall be have a nominal voltage of 48V with a capacity between 50Ah to 150Ah and shall be used at a test bench.

Cell measurement *NEMO_SYS_e41cc626*

links outgoing: None

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_52e2608f*

is related to: *NEMO_SYS_78db8cec, NEMO_SYS_df2dcc5d*

The system shall be able to perform an *EIS* measurement for a single cell under load and no load conditions.
The system shall be able to perform a voltage measurement for a single cell with an update rate up to 100 Hz and and temperature measurement for a single cell at 1 Hz.
The system shall be able to perform a module current measurement up to 100 Hz.

Communication *NEMO_SYS_6bab3c1b*

links outgoing: None

links incoming: None

is related to: *NEMO_SYS_30b221e9*, *NEMO_SYS_8e55aad6*, *NEMO_SYS_0a31a087*, *NEMO_SYS_9cfc0bfd*

The communication between the *CPU* and the *AFE* (see figure [System concept zBMS \(NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb\)](#) and [System concept zBMS+ \(NEMO_SYS_812d48ac\)](#)) shall be realized with a wired connection in a first step, and shall be replaced by a wireless solution in a second step.

Data collection *NEMO_SYS_dc11ff2f*

links outgoing: , , , ,

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_a261eeea*

is related to: *NEMO_SYS_78db8cec*, *NEMO_SYS_0a31a087*, *NEMO_SYS_1cebfb2a*, *NEMO_SYS_5264cc54*

The system shall be able to collect cell data like voltage, current, temperature and *EIS* related data. Current and cell voltage measurement must be synchronized. The collected data shall be saved in a cloud storage. The system shall use the [BattINFO](#) ontology.

Balancing/Bypassing *NEMO_SYS_dc59c671*

links outgoing: None

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_15e48db0*

The system shall be able to balance each cell via passive balancing (*SOC*) and active cell bypassing (*SOH*). The active balancing in combination with the *SOH* algorithms shall extend the module lifetime by 20 % at 80 % remaining capacity.

Distributed computing of algorithms *NEMO_SYS_ecb106a9*

links outgoing: None

is related to: *NEMO_SYS_78db8cec*, *NEMO_SYS_0a31a087*, *NEMO_SYS_1cebfb2a*, *NEMO_SYS_53a8ea28*

The system shall be able to perform algorithms on the collected data. The calculations shall be performed on the cell measurement controller (*CMC*) and central processing unit (*CPU*, see figure [System concept zBMS \(NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb\)](#) and [System concept zBMS+ \(NEMO_SYS_812d48ac\)](#)) as well as in the cloud.

Algorithms - Standard SOx *NEMO_SYS_18606edf*

links outgoing: None

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_c6aaf740*, *NEMO_SYS_cbca87d8*, *NEMO_SYS_67160af1*, *NEMO_SYS_10e9ad72*, *NEMO_SYS_c15fd091*, *NEMO_SYS_480cf80c*, *NEMO_SYS_1c9cf00e*, *NEMO_SYS_6b288abb*, *NEMO_SYS_cd10f704*, *NEMO_SYS_ed91f29a*

The system shall be able to calculate default *SOx* algorithms based on IAV standard. This will contain *SOC* and *SOH*.

Algorithms - Physic-based models *NEMO_SYS_49269662*

links outgoing: ,

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_52e2608f*

The system shall be able to calculate different *SOx* by using physic-based models under consideration of *EIS* measurement.

- *SOC* estimation shall use a *P2D* and *P-ECM* model
- *SOH* estimation shall use a *MSM* and *P-ECM* model
- *SOP* estimation shall use a *P2D* and *P-ECM* model

Algorithms - Data-driven models *NEMO_SYS_2a7f5738*

links outgoing: , ,

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_52e2608f*

The system shall be able to calculate data-driven battery ageing models.

- Pure data-driven ageing model including *RUL* prediction
- Hybrid physics and data-driven ageing model for *SOH*
- *EIS* based core cell temperature estimator
- *EIS* based *SOS* estimation via GPR or based on *P-ECM* model
- Cell failure and *TR* detection

Testing [NEMO_SYS_4ae76299](#)

links outgoing: , ,

links incoming: None

is related to: [NEMO_SYS_39ccd240](#), [NEMO_SYS_4d69ca22](#), [NEMO_SYS_6cb92f5f](#), [NEMO_SYS_9cfc0bfd](#)

The system shall provide data from a test bench to support the algorithm development. The cells shall be characterized and be cycled using current and temperature profiles to provide ageing data.

The zBMS module shall be cycled for 18 months and zBMS+ module shall be cycled for 12 months.

The accuracy of the proposed algorithms shall be as followed:

- *SOC MAPE* < 1 % after 18 months
- *SOH MAPE* < 1 % after 18 months
- *RUL* < 3 % after 18 months
- Cell failure and *TR* events can be detected with 100 % accuracy

Reference measurement methods [NEMO_SYS_aeead2e9](#)

links outgoing: ,

links incoming: None

The system shall provide a reference measurement method for *SOx* and *RUL* determination used for model comparison.

The comparison shall be performed between the *P2D*, *P-ECM* and default *SOx* algorithms.

Housing [NEMO_SYS_e92fee52](#)

links outgoing: , , , ,

The system shall be put into a simple housing to ensure mechanical integrity for the [Testing](#) ([NEMO_SYS_4ae76299](#)). Note that for the testing at module level, no thermal control is foreseen to be embedded into the housing.

Evolution *NEMO_SYS_2bbbe928*

links outgoing: None

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb*, *NEMO_SYS_812d48ac*,

The system shall evolve during the project. The evolution stages are named *zBMS* and *zBMS+*. The first step *zBMS* shall focus on cell-based EIS acquisition and gathering data to the cloud. The second step *zBMS+* shall focus on the wireless communication and active balancing possibilities of the *CMC*s as well as an integrated version of all other components.

Overrides *NEMO_SYS_6ac4387e*

links outgoing: None

Due to setup, quick test, demonstration and development the system shall have some simple controls to override pack current value, status for contactors and supply rails as well as activation signals. It has to be possible to disable override functionality in a safe way.

USE CASES

2.1 Introduction

Lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries have significantly benefited from R&D investment aimed at commercializing their use in the electronics and transport applications. Li-ion batteries are also emerging as one of the fastest growing battery technologies for grid applications. They are presently deployed globally in a variety of applications, from small scale distributed systems (1-10 kW/kWh) to large fast-responding systems for frequency services and energy time shifting (1-50 MW/MWh).

The two use cases for stationary and automotive applications are considered to derive requirements. Note that the results of the NEMO project are predominantly dedicated to the automotive use case.

2.2 Automotive

Automotive *NEMO_SYS_5d7fe8fc*

An *EVB* is a rechargeable high-voltage battery used to power the electric motors of a *BEV*, a *PHEV* or *HEV*. These batteries are designed for high poer-to-weight ratio and energy density.

Fig. 1: The above image is copied from IFX homepage.

Normative and legal boundary conditions *NEMO_SYS_168422d6*

is related to: None

- mostly defined per company standards
- ISO 12405-4:2018-07 1
NEMO_NORM_ISO12405-4
Electrically propelled road vehicles
Test specification for lithium-ion traction battery packs and systems
Part 4: Performance testing
- ISO 19453-6:2020-7 2
NEMO_NORM_ISO19453-6
Road vehicles
Environmental conditions and testing
for electrical and electronic equipment for drive system of electric propulsion vehicles
Part 6: Traction battery packs and systems
- IEC 62660-1:2018-12 3
NEMO_NORM_IEC62660-1
Secondary lithium-ion cells for the propulsion of electric road vehicles
Part 1: Performance testing
- IEC 62660-2:2018-12 4
NEMO_NORM_IEC62660-2
Secondary lithium-ion cells for the propulsion of electric road vehicles
Part 2: Reliability and abuse testing
- ISO 27145-x 5
NEMO_NORM_ISO27145-x
Road vehicles
Implementation of World-Wide Harmonized On-Board Diagnostics communication requirements
- UN ECE R100 6
NEMO_NORM_UN_ECE_R100
Uniform provisions concerning the approval of battery electric vehicles
with regards to specific requirements for the construction and functional safety
- GB/T 31484-2015 7
NEMO_NORM_GB/T31484
Cycle life requirements and test methods for traction battery
- ISO 20653:2013-02 8
NEMO_NORM_ISO20653
Road vehicles
Degrees of protection (IP-Code).
Protection of electrical equipment against foreign objects, water and access
- ISO 26262-x:2018-12 9
NEMO_NORM_ISO26262-x
Road vehicles
functional safety

Functions *NEMO_SYS_c9d83387*

The following output quantities shall be calculated:

- State of Charge (*SOC*), which is crucial for determining how much energy is available and when to initiate charging or discharging operations.
- State of Health (*SOH*), which represents the battery's overall health and remaining capacity compared to its original capacity when new. This information helps assess the battery's performance and determine if it requires maintenance or replacement.
- State of Power (*SOP*)
- Remaining useful life (*RUL*)
- State of Safety (*SOS*)

Other required functions:

- Error handling: The BMS continuously checks for any abnormalities or faults within the battery system and communicates these issues to the user or higher-level control systems for appropriate action.
- Emergency shut-off: In case of emergencies or critical conditions, the BMS can trigger safety measures such as disconnecting the battery or isolating faulty cells.
- Logging: The BMS shall have a logging mechanism in order to log parameters, that might be of interest for the project.

Monitoring *NEMO_SYS_28abee12*

The following quantities shall be monitored:

- Cell voltage
- Module voltage
- Cell temperature
- Module current

Functional safety *NEMO_SYS_b5b98f3d*

- Basic requirements and approval: see UN ECE R100 (NEMO_SYS_168422d6.6)
- Development process: see ISO 26262-x:2018-12 (NEMO_SYS_168422d6.9)

Protection *NEMO_SYS_b631909f*

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_175f6653*

The electrical system requires the following protection:

- Over and under voltage, which can lead to cell damage or pack failure.
- Over current, preventing excessive currents that could lead to overheating or other hazardous situations
- Short circuit current
- Over and under temperature, To prevent thermal runaway.
- Balance the individual cells

The mechanical system requires the following protection:

- Typical IP code: up to IP69 (dust-tight, high-pressure steam-jet)
- Test methods: see ISO 20653:2013-02 (NEMO_SYS_168422d6.8)

Temperature *NEMO_SYS_8fc8927a*

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_51f4ea02*

Min/max ambient temperatures and temperature distribution according to mission profile of target country. E.g. world profile: -20°C to +40°C

- Temperature range cells (these are typical values and have to be adapted to the cell safety datasheet):
 - Minimum: -20 °C
 - Maximum: +60 °C
- Temperature range cells during fast charging:
 - Minimum: +5 °C
 - Maximum: +45 °C
- Temperature range hardware:
 - Minimum: -40 °C
 - Maximum: +125 °C

Voltage *NEMO_SYS_885f3492*

Usually 400V or 800V system voltage for *BEV*, *PHEV* and *HEV*-traction HV batteries. For 800V systems: configuration changeable between 400V and 800V (charging infrastructure). Note that 400/800V battery systems are composed of modules with typically 48V system voltage, which is the focus of the NEMO project. For mild hybrids abs electric two/three wheelers, batteries 48V are typical. For the general automotive energy system 12V are usually used.

Current *NEMO_SYS_41f4fb05*

Max. current depending on vehicle weight, cell capabilities and driving mode.

Max. current is usually linked to the battery capacity, e.g. 5C, which corresponds to typically up to 500A or even 1000A (high power vehicles).

Typical charge and discharge profiles: see automotive driving profiles (WLTP, CATC).

Cycle count *NEMO_SYS_b923727e*

Typical number of charging cycles: **tbd**

Test methods: see GB/T 31484-2015 (NEMO_SYS_168422d6.7)

Life time *NEMO_SYS_b4cdd37a*

Life time according to mission profile.

Typical range: 8 years up to 15 years.

Active time *NEMO_SYS_ad3101fe*

- Active time according to mission profile.
- Subdivided in driving, pre conditioning (on grid), AC charging, DC (fast) charging, bidi charging, balancing, sleep.
- Typical driving time: 8000 hours.
- Pre conditioning: **tbd** hours.
- Typical AC charging time: **tbd** hours.
- Typical DC (fast) charging time: **tbd** hours.
- Typical bidi charging time: **tbd** hours.
- Typical balancing time: depending on cell quality, charging and balancing strategy, usually > 50% of sum of charging times

Sleep time: difference between life time and sum of active times.

Mechanical loads *NEMO_SYS_1af9c236*

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_b8bad726*

- Vibration: 27,8 m/s² / 10...2000 Hz / 8 h
- Shock: half-sinusoidal / 500 m/s² / 6 ms / 10 shocks per test direction
- Crush: 150 mm / force release at 1/3 voltage drop OR 15% deformation OR 1k times cell weight
- Test methods: see IEC 62660-2:2018-12 (NEMO_SYS_168422d6.4)

Note that mechanical loads will not be tested nor validated within the NEMO project.

Diagnosis *NEMO_SYS_9c5d5153*

OBD is mandatory for a final product. For its implementation see ISO 27145-x (NEMO_SYS_168422d6.5)
Note that OBD will not be implemented within the NEMO project.

2.3 Stationary

Stationary *NEMO_SYS_1d3e5c05*

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_51f4ea02*, *NEMO_SYS_db38ad39*, *NEMO_SYS_b8bad726*, *NEMO_SYS_175f6653*, *NEMO_SYS_66394475*, *NEMO_SYS_efabb291*, *NEMO_SYS_fbe87f1f*
is related to: None

BESS are rechargeable batteries that can store energy from different sources and discharge it when needed. *BESS* consist of one or more batteries and can be used to balance the electric grid, provide backup power, and improve grid stability. The term stationary battery applies to cells and batteries which are designed for fixed service locations and which are permanently connected to the load and to dc power supply. A very important characteristic of the stationary batteries is that they are maintenance free.

Our use case shall not cover any power conditioning functionality (e.g. grid voltage or frequency regulation). The stationary use case requirements should be covered by the automotive use case requirements.

Normative and legal boundary conditions *NEMO_SYS_8f0722fd*

Normative and legal boundary conditions are defined in

- IEC 61427-2
- NF EN 50272

Scientific literature:

- 2nd Life Use Cases
- 2nd Life PV ESS
- ESS Load Profiles

Functions *NEMO_SYS_a3148d96*

The following output quantities shall be calculated:

- State of Charge (*SOC*), which is crucial for determining how much energy is available and when to initiate charging or discharging operations.
- State of Health (*SOH*), which represents the battery's overall health and remaining capacity compared to its original capacity when new. This information helps assess the battery's performance and determine if it requires maintenance or replacement.
- State of Power (*SOP*)
- Remaining useful life (*RUL*)
- State of Safety (*SOS*)

Other required functions shall be available:

- Error handling: The BMS continuously checks for any abnormalities or faults within the battery system and communicates these issues to the user or higher-level control systems for appropriate action.
- Emergency shut-off: In case of emergencies or critical conditions, the BMS can trigger safety measures such as disconnecting the battery or isolating faulty cells.
- Logging: The BMS shall have a logging mechanism in order to log parameters, that might be of interest for the project.

Monitoring *NEMO_SYS_74ad7137*

The following quantities shall be monitored:

- Cell voltage
- Module voltage
- Cell temperature
- Module current

All monitored data and system status to the cloud via a standard protocol.

Protection *NEMO_SYS_09e071ee*

- Over and under voltage, which can lead to cell damage or pack failure.
- Over current, preventing excessive currents that could lead to overheating or other hazardous situations
- Short circuit current
- Over and under temperature, To prevent thermal runaway.
- Balance the individual cells

Operating Modes *NEMO_SYS_138fbf57*

- Virtual synchronous generator: This mode of operation makes the PCS work as a voltage source converter. Under this mode, the BESS shall be able to provide its own voltage and frequency to an islanded grid, or to work in parallel with the utility grid in the grid-connected mode.
- Active and reactive power control: In this mode of operation, PCS controls the output active and reactive powers supplied to the grid following their reference values which may be set locally or remotely.
- Voltage and frequency control: In this mode of operation, PCS controls its own voltage and frequency, enabling it to create an islanded grid. Voltage and frequency control is possible when the PCS is in the voltage source operating mode.
- Voltage and frequency droop for parallel operation: The voltage droop allows reactive power sharing when the BESS is in an islanded mode or paralleled with other voltage sources. The frequency droop allows active power sharing when the BESS is in an islanded mode or paralleled with other voltage sources.

3.1 Architecture

System concept zBMS *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_2bbbe928*

is related to: *NEMO_SYS_46a436ed, NEMO_SYS_4292ca81, NEMO_SYS_e085f55d, NEMO_SYS_6b56363c, NEMO_SYS_45c509fd, NEMO_SYS_78db8cec, NEMO_SYS_30b221e9, NEMO_SYS_df2dcc5d, NEMO_SYS_0a31a087, NEMO_SYS_1cebfb2a, NEMO_SYS_8acb6b1c, NEMO_SYS_c4ac9210, NEMO_SYS_1ca63335, NEMO_SYS_26c81d85, NEMO_SYS_5264cc54, NEMO_SYS_53a8ea28*

System concept of zBMS battery system divided into main components:

- single cells - *CEL*
- single cell measurement board with measurements (voltage, temperature and EIS) and wired communication to CPU - *CMC*
- main board with CPU and wired communication to CMC - *BMC*
- current and voltage measurement at system level - *IVT*
- contactor with pre-charge and fuse - *CNT*
- power supply - *PWR*
- cloud storage - *CLD*

To setup the zBMS as fast as possible no hardware shall be developed. The system shall be setup from available development boards for the *AFE* and *CPU*.

System concept zBMS+ *NEMO_SYS_812d48ac*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_2bbbe928*

is related to: *NEMO_SYS_8e55aad6*

System concept of zBMS+ battery system divided into main components:

- single cells - *CEL*
- single cell measurement board with measurements (voltage, temperature and EIS), wireless communication to CPU, active balancing and cell bypassing - *CMC*
- main board with CPU and wireless communication to CMC- *BMC*
- current and voltage measurement at system level - *IVT*
- contactor with pre-charge and fuse - *CNT*
- power supply - *PWR*
- cloud storage and algorithms - *CLD*

3.2 Components

3.2.1 Cells

Number of cells *NEMO_SYS_46a436ed*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CEL*

The battery system shall contain 12 cells to achieve a nominal voltage of 48V.

Chemistry *NEMO_SYS_4292ca81*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CEL*

The cell chemistry shall be NMC523 or later.

Capacity *NEMO_SYS_e085f55d*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CEL*

is related to: *NEMO_SYS_868e55b6*

- Min. capacity of 50Ah per cell.
- Max. capacity of 150Ah per cell.

No hard preference but considering the testing effort, any cell below 100 Ah capacity would be good (ideally <75 Ah).

Form factor *NEMO_SYS_6b56363c*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CEL*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CMC*

The system shall use prismatic cells with tabs on the same side.

The system shall not use prismatic cells with opposite connections, neither pouch cells.

Connections *NEMO_SYS_45c509fd*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CEL*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CMC*

The cell connectors shall be tabs for welding or screw terminals.

Cycle life *NEMO_SYS_5b484aef*

Typical cycle life of the selected NMC technology should be > 2000 cycles (100% *DOD*) or > 3000 cycles (80% *DOD*) at 25 °C.

Charge-Discharge rates *NEMO_SYS_81924ce5*

The selected cell type should have high charge-discharge rate capabilities (continuous).

- Charge rate > 2C
- Discharge rate > 3C

Availability *NEMO_SYS_3cf1f6b7*

Cells should be ideally available at M6/OCT-2023, thus, purchase and/or delivery time (lead time) should be < 1 month.

Costs *NEMO_SYS_747c72e0*

Purchasing cost should be within budget.

Battery cell selection *NEMO_SYS_0b98edcf*

A prismatic NMC631 cell from Westart 75 Ah with a nominal capacity of 75 Ah and M6 screws terminal shall be used.

NEMO_DATASHEET_PHEV75Ah

Parameter	Condition	Value
Dimension (T x W x H)	without terminals	(22.8 x 220.6 x 105.4)mm
	with terminals	(22.8 x 220.6 x 107.4)mm
Minimum capacity @ 25°C	0.33C	75Ah
	1C	72Ah
Nominal voltage @ 25°C	1C	3.72V
Operating voltage		2.8V - 4.35V
Impedance	25°C, 1 kHz	0.55mΩ
DCR	25°C, 2C DC 10s, 50% SOC	0.95mΩ
Max. pulse charge current	10s	8C
Max. pulse discharge current	10s	8C
Weight		1.22kg ± 0.05kg
Cycle life	1C/1C, 10% - 95% SOC	> 4000 cycles
Operating temperatures		-30°C ... +55°C
Storage temperatures		-40°C ... +60°C

3.2.2 Single cell measurement board

Measurement *NEMO_SYS_17adf79e*

links incoming: *NEMO_SYS_116cf9c4*, *NEMO_SYS_a261eeea*

The CMC shall be able to measure the following values:

- EIS via NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9010EP
- Cell voltage via NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9010EP or NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9012DQU
 - Cell voltage and module current should be measured synchronously
- Cell temperature, **not** possible via NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9010EP
- Cell temperature, possible via NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9012DQU or master board

Analog Front End (AFE) *NEMO_SYS_78db8cec*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_e41cc626*, *NEMO_SYS_dc11ff2f*, *NEMO_SYS_ecb106a9*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb*.*CMC*

As *AFE* the NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9010EP from Infineon shall be used. This device provides simultaneously voltage and *EIS* measurement of a single cell. If the measurement requirements are not met by the NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9010EP, dedicated HW can be used.

Wired communication *NEMO_SYS_30b221e9*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_6bab3c1b*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb*.*CMC*

For the wired communication the transceiver NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9015DQU from Infineon shall be used. This device provides an *UART* interface to the *CPU* and the two wired isoUART interface to the *AFE*.

Wireless communication *NEMO_SYS_8e55aad6*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_6bab3c1b*, *NEMO_SYS_812d48ac*.*CMC*

Wireless communication via e.g. *BLE*, Wi-Fi, ...

Power supply *NEMO_SYS_df2dcc5d*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_e41cc626*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb*.*CMC*

The *CMS* board be powered from the cell itself.

Balancing/Bypassing zBMS+ *NEMO_SYS_15e48db0*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_dc59c671*

Active balancing or bypassing is realized according to patented CSEM approach .

This approach foresees to combine *EIS* sensing with a cell reconfiguration possibility that allows to switch in or out each individual cell of a string as illustrated in the illustration below [1].

The switching of individual cells of a battery string is triggered based on signals that are derived from the *EIS* measurement and for the following objectives:

- Balance *SOC* of all cells in the string, e.g., cells with lower *SOC* do not participate in discharging
- Balance *SOH* of all cells in the string, e.g., cells with lower *SOH* do not participate in discharging

Additional considerations of importance for the physical realization of the switching circuitry include:

- Support of up to 4C switching current is required to ensure switching under load
- Appropriate timing to avoid string opening or cell short-circuits is to be foreseen
- Support for ASIL-C/D requires redundancy of two switches in series

[1] Juan Alberto Romero, Pol Paradell, Lluís Trilla, “Advanced modular battery management system for next generation of research platforms,” ICCEP, Toronto, Italy, July 2023

Concept of cell temperature measurement *NEMO_SYS_116cf9c4*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_17adf79e*

For zBMS:

- Cell temperature measurement shall be done for each cell via a *NTC* resistor.
- Signal sampling shall be done via 3 pieces of NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9012DQU, each equipped with 4 *NTC* inputs.
- Supply voltage for the NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9012DQU shall be derived directly from cell stack (B+/-) or from host supply (*CPU*).
- Supply voltage for the NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9012DQU shall be in parallel for all three ASICs.
- All NEMO_DATASHEET_TLE9012DQU shall be inserted into the DaisyChain line for communication.

For zBMS+:

- Local processing of continuously acquired *EIS* signal on *CPU* for core temperature estimation (e.g. distribution processing)

Mounting concept *NEMO_SYS_cd2a5764*

The *CMS* shall be mounted on top of each single cell.

Challenges:

- Implementation of suitable designs and joining techniques that ensure low-ohmic connections of all parts
- Avoidance of parasitic effects on the multiple printed circuit board (PCB) of the system (battery connectors, current loops, etc.).

3.2.3 Main CPU board

CPU *NEMO_SYS_0a31a087*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_6bab3c1b*, *NEMO_SYS_dc11ff2f*, *NEMO_SYS_ecb106a9*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb*.*BMC*

As main *CPU* the next generation *NEMO_DATASHEET_TC49x_UserManual* from Infineon shall be used. This *CPU* provides up to six cores, a parallel processing unit and most of the common connectivity interfaces like *UART*, *I2C*, *SPI*, *CAN*, and Ethernet.

The main *CPU* board shall be powered via an external power supply.

3.2.4 System current and voltage measurement

IVT *NEMO_SYS_1cebfb2a*

links incoming: None

relates: *NEMO_SYS_dc11ff2f*, *NEMO_SYS_ecb106a9*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.IVT*

- Measurement of overall system current, voltage and isolation resistance shall be done via NEMO_DATASHEET_IVT3.
- Current measurement shall be done at the negative terminal of the battery.
- System voltages shall be measured at stack B+/-, after fuse, after main contactor+ and main contactor- and between pre-charge contactor and pre-charge resistor.
- Isolation resistance shall be measured after main contactor +/- against external supply voltage ground (KL31).
- Power supply shall be derived from external power supply (KL30/KL31).
- Power supply shall be switchable.
- Communication interface shall be high speed *CAN* connected to *CPU* main board.

3.2.5 Contactor and Fuse

Contactor *NEMO_SYS_8acb6b1c*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CNT*

The system shall be able to perform at least an unipolar galvanic isolated disconnection of the battery voltage at the external terminals.

Fuse *NEMO_SYS_c4ac9210*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CNT*

The system shall have a fuse to protect the system/wire/cell during over current and external short circuits.

pre-charge *NEMO_SYS_1ca63335*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CNT*

The system shall be able to pre-charge via an external circuit up to the battery voltage prior the main contactor are being closed to reduce the difference voltage during connection.

3.2.6 Power supply

Low voltage power supply *NEMO_SYS_26c81d85*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.PWR*

The system shall be powered by an external power supply with a nominal voltage of 12V.

3.2.7 Cloud

Cloud storage *NEMO_SYS_5264cc54*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_dc11ff2f*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CLD*

The system shall provide a cloud storage to save all measurements.

The system shall use the BattINFO ontology. It shall be used for the definition of physical measurement values (U,I,T) and the chemistry type of the cell.

The system shall provide an interface/API to the cloud.

The data shall be public available.

- How to use BattINFO ontology?
 - It shall be used for the definition of physical measurement values (U,I,T) and the chemistry type of the cell.
- Which data to the cloud/Amount of data.
 - All data shall be stored.
- Which data is produced (data types, tables) → see *Models*
- Which data format/compression?
 - Store in a database. No explicit compression.
- Database and backup strategy
 - Timescale, which is a PostgreSQL-derivation for time series as database shall be used. This has also plugins for Telegraf, Kafka and batch ingress CSV files.
 - Alternatively InfluxDB could be used.
- Open Data
 - The data shall be put either as SQLITE or csv format on an open data website. No open access to the production database itself.
 - Regular snapshots (e.g. once a month) can be published.
- Protocol/API
 - For ingestion: At first, an asynchronous method will be implemented. Data is sent in regular intervals as CSV to the cloud and then batch ingressed.
 - Later, tools like Telegraf and Kafka to allow real-time streaming of data will be implemented.
 - For query to build models: Connect to database, make queries using SQL. Alternative: Move all data into SQLITE database, download SQLITE file, query locally.

Cloud algorithms *NEMO_SYS_53a8ea28*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_ecb106a9*, *NEMO_SYS_b8e0b2cb.CLD*

The system shall provide a cloud with the possibility to calculate any kind of algorithms with access to the stored measurement data.

The system shall provide the possibility to execute all necessary files/frameworks/programmes.

The system should work with:

- Matlab
- Python (preferred)
- C/C++ (preferred)
- Comsol (probably the most difficult and rather to avoid)

3.3 Environmental Conditions

Temperature *NEMO_SYS_51f4ea02*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_1d3e5c05*, *NEMO_SYS_8fc8927a*

The battery system shall be used only on battery test benches. The environment temperature shall be in a range from 5 °C to 40 °C.

Other requirements from -

- Automotive use case:
 - Cells: -20 °C to +60 °C
 - Fast charging: +5 °C to +45 °C
 - Hardware: -40 °C to +125 °C
- Stationary use case: 0 °C to +45 °C

Humidity *NEMO_SYS_db38ad39*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_1d3e5c05*

The system shall be used within < 95% relative humidity (RH).

- Automotive use case: < 95 % RH
- Stationary use case: < 95 % RH

Vibration *NEMO_SYS_b8bad726*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_1d3e5c05*, *NEMO_SYS_1af9c236*

The zBMS and zBMS+ modules system shall withstand vibrations with peak ground accelerations of 0.5 g.

- Automotive use case: 27,8 m/s² / 10...2000 Hz / 8 h
- Stationary use case: < 0.5 g

Protection *NEMO_SYS_175f6653*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_1d3e5c05*, *NEMO_SYS_b631909f*

The zBMS shall meet the degree of protection IP20, see [IP ratings](#).

The zBMS+ shall meet the degree of protection IP20, see [IP ratings](#).

- Automotive use case: IP69 (dust-tight, high-pressure steam-jet)
- Stationary use case: IP51

FUNCTIONS

4.1 Interfaces

Electrical interfaces *NEMO_SYS_80bb0e34*

The system shall have the following electrical interfaces:

- HV connection, high voltage and high current
 - LV connection, low voltage power supply
-

Mechanical interfaces *NEMO_SYS_b7ebe840*

The system shall have the following mechanical interfaces.

Add screw points locks or something like this to connect the battery case on the test bench.

Communication interfaces *NEMO_SYS_639f559e*

The system shall have the following external communication interfaces:

- *CAN*
 - Ethernet
 - *UART*
 - Digital IOs
 - Display and LEDs
-

Wireless communication *NEMO_SYS_b045a3e1*

For the zBMS+ demonstrator wireless communication is foreseen. In addition to the specification of the data signals, the required data rate for the wireless communication link as well as the acceptable transmission errors rates and acceptable delay times must be specified. For these points the following items need to be considered for the selection of a suitable communication system:

Data exchange from CMS to master

- Data rate mainly determined by 100Hz for current and voltage signals plus protocol overhead, delay of max. 250 ms
- Failure indication signal (2 bytes) is rarely transmitted but very time-critical; the use of a transmission service guarantees mechanism is required!

Signal name	max. delay	Error rate tolerance
Cell voltage	250 ms	Can loose up to 50% within max. up to 30 second period, e.g., every second sample
Cell temperature	250 ms	Can loose up to 50% within max. up to 30 second period, e.g., every second sample
Cell impedance	250 ms	Can loose up to 50% within max. up to 30 second period, e.g., every second sample
Module current	250 ms	Can loose up to 50% within max. up to 30 second period, e.g., every second sample
Failure indication	250 ms	No loss admitted, max. allowed delay 250 ms

Data exchange from master to CMS

- Only low-rate traffic for command signal; data rate considerations are therefore not critical
- Command signals are not time-critical and delay up to 1 second can be tolerated, but transmission service guarantee are required, e.g., via acknowledge and retransmission until success.

signal name	max. delay	error rate tolerance
do EIS	250 ms	no loss admitted
do core temperature	250 ms	no loss admitted
do bypass	250 ms	no loss admitted

The following table provides and overview of different wireless communication technologies and comments their capability to support up to 400 CMS nodes in parallel (extract of CSEM feasibility study). The proprietary AirTDMA protocol or the GTS version of the IEEE 802.15.4 protocol are suitable candidates for the implementation of the zBMS+ demonstrator.

Blue- tooth classic	Bluetooth LE	AirTDMA	IEEE 802.15.4	Thread
Limited to 7 slave devices with 1 Hz traffic [1].	Limited to 20 peripherals. If using advertisements, no collision limited to 20 devices with 1 Hz traffic [1].	CSEM proprietary, but flexible. Can accomodate 400 nodes with 1 ms slot duration and 50 ms beacon period. Leaves 500 slots second for sporadic traffic and repetitions.	Up to 16 channels in 2.4 GHz band. Guaranteed time slots (GTS) - TDMA. No GTS with CSMA/CA non beacon-enabled.	Comes on top of IEEE802.15.4 with 6LoWPAN, IP routing and UDP. large overhead and not useful for zBMS technology.

In addition to delay and criticality constraints, the data transmission needs to be guaranteed for all locations of **4.1 CMS interfaces** within the battery housing. The CSEM feasibility study showed that this can be achieved via suitable channel selection within the 2.4 GHz band, e.g., channels with sufficient link quality can be identified via suitable start-up procedure.

Thermal conditioning interfaces [NEMO_SYS_244d7aee](#)

The system shall not have any active thermal conditioning features. The only way for conditioning is the free convection around the battery case.

4.2 Performance

Voltage [NEMO_SYS_66394475](#)

links outgoing: [NEMO_SYS_1d3e5c05](#)

The battery system shall contain 12 cells to build a 48V system.
The following typical voltage specifications are provided as reference.

- Automotive use case: 400 V to 800 V
- Stationary use case: 48 V to 800 V

Current [NEMO_SYS_efabb291](#)

links outgoing: [NEMO_SYS_1d3e5c05](#)

The zBMS and zBMS+ modules need to provide charge and discharge currents that are in alignment with the specifications of the finally used battery cells in these modules, see also [Battery cell selection \(NEMO_SYS_0b98edcf\)](#).

The following typical current specifications are provided as reference.

- Automotive use case
 - Continuous charge current: 100 A
 - Pulse charge current: 300 A
 - Continuous discharge current: 100 A
 - Pulse discharge current: 400 A
- Stationary use case
 - Continuous charge current: 16 A
 - Pulse charge current: 16 A
 - Continuous discharge current: 16 A
 - Pulse discharge current: 16 A

Power [NEMO_SYS_fbe87f1f](#)

links outgoing: [NEMO_SYS_1d3e5c05](#)

The zBMS and zBMS+ modules need to provide charge and discharge powers that are in alignment with the specifications of the finally used battery cells in these modules, see also [Battery cell selection \(NEMO_SYS_0b98edcf\)](#).

The following typical power specifications are provided as reference.

- Automotive use case
 - Continuous charge power: 4.8 kW
 - Pulse charge power: 14.4 kW
 - Continuous discharge power: 4.8 kW
 - Pulse discharge power: 19.2 kW
- Stationary use case
 - Continuous charge power: 760 W
 - Pulse charge power: 760 W
 - Continuous discharge power: 760 W
 - Pulse discharge power: 760 W

EIS [NEMO_SYS_52e2608f](#)

links outgoing: [NEMO_SYS_e41cc626](#), [NEMO_SYS_49269662](#), [NEMO_SYS_2a7f5738](#)

The system shall perform [EIS](#) under the following boundary conditions:

- Cell voltage: 2 V to 4.3 V
- Temperature: -20 °C to 50 °C
- Current load profiles
 - in idle condition: EIS to be triggered when battery cells are in relaxed conditions, e.g. 1h after the last use
 - under load: EIS to be triggered under all load conditions according to algorithm needs, see also [Models](#).

The system shall perform [EIS](#) with following parameters:

- Excitation frequency:
 - 20 mHz to 5 kHz; 10 frequencies per decade;
 - The excitation frequency range must include the frequency that corresponds to the characteristic frequency of the [SEI](#); this frequency is expected to be in the range of a few hundred Hz
- Excitation current amplitude: typically 5% of cell capacity, e.g. 5 A RMS for the selected cells, see also [Battery cell selection \(NEMO_SYS_0b98edcf\)](#).
- Excitation current waveform: sinusoidal
- Impedance magnitude accuracy: $\pm 10 \mu\Omega$
- Impedance phase accuracy: $\pm 1^\circ$

Synchronicity of current and voltage measurement *NEMO_SYS_a261eee*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_17adf79e*, *NEMO_SYS_dc11ff2f*

The system shall measure the module current and the individual cell voltages synchronously. The synchronous measurement is required for the battery models, e.g. cell resistance estimation. The synchronization error shall be less than 1 ms.

Also individual EIS excitation current and cell voltage shall be measured with synchronization error less than 10µs.

Capacity *NEMO_SYS_868e55b6*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_e085f55d*

The system shall have a capacity of 75 Ah, see also [Battery cell selection \(NEMO_SYS_0b98edcf\)](#).

4.3 States

Sleep *NEMO_SYS_39ccd240*

links incoming: None

relates: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_4ae76299*

The system shall be able to go into sleep mode, where the contactors are opened, communication is inactive and cell measurement is inactive.

Standby *NEMO_SYS_4d69ca22*

relates: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_4ae76299*

The system shall be able to go into standby state, where the contactors are opened and communication is active and cell measurement can be activated.

Active *NEMO_SYS_6cb92f5f*

links incoming: None

relates: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_4ae76299*

The system shall be able to going into active state, where the contactors are closed and current demand is possible.

Safe state *NEMO_SYS_9cfc0bfd*

links incoming: None

relates: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_4ae76299*, *NEMO_SYS_6bab3c1b*

The system shall be able to going into safe state, where the contactors are opened and no current demand is allowed. The safe state shall be visible and signaled by a message to the upper level.

4.4 Safety

Voltage *NEMO_SYS_c6aaf740*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_18606edf*

The system shall going to Safe state (*NEMO_SYS_9cfc0bfd*) if the voltage of a single cell is not within an upper and lower voltage limit, see also Battery cell selection (*NEMO_SYS_0b98edcf*).

Current *NEMO_SYS_cbca87d8*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_18606edf*

The system shall going to Safe state (*NEMO_SYS_9cfc0bfd*) if an over current occurs, see also Battery cell selection (*NEMO_SYS_0b98edcf*).

Temperature *NEMO_SYS_67160af1*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_cc7e60a9*, *NEMO_SYS_18606edf*

The system shall going to Safe state (*NEMO_SYS_9cfc0bfd*) if the temperature of a single cell is not within an upper and lower temperature limit, see also Battery cell selection (*NEMO_SYS_0b98edcf*).

5.1 P2D

EIS driven P2D *NEMO_SYS_fce1b485*

The development of an *EIS* driven *P2D* model relies on one-dimensional partial differential equations, encompassing parameter dependencies that are subsequently transformed into the frequency domain. The governing equations comprehensively incorporate critical aspects, including:

- Mass balance equation (diffusion and migration)
- Butler-Volmer kinetics
- Fickian diffusion
- Double-layer effects
- Appropriate boundary conditions
- Integrate the relevant aging mechanism/parameters including electrolyte decomposition, transition metal dissolution, etc.

EIS driven P2D - Parameter estimation *NEMO_SYS_3fad5775*

Based on Cyclic voltameter and *EIS* measurement the following parameters will be estimated.

- Reaction rate constants
- Diffusion coefficient of Lithium-ion
- Ionic conductivity of the electrolyte
- Electronic conductivity of the electrodes
- SEI layer resistance
- An advanced algorithm will be devised to efficiently estimate multiple parameters simultaneously.

EIS driven P2D - Model validation *NEMO_SYS_dbee51fe*

Validation of the model will involve a comprehensive comparison between the simulated *EIS* data and the corresponding experimental spectra under diverse conditions, encompassing cycling stress factor variations like *SOC* range, *DOD*, temperature, C-rates and more.

EIS driven P2D - Model Input & Output *NEMO_SYS_870e47c5*

Abbreviations used in the model overview table: Meas = Measured; Calc = Calculated; I = Input; O = Output; UpdR = Update rate; DatTyp = Data type; Flt = Float; FltArr = Float array; Prcsn = Precision; d = Day;

Parameter	Class	Source	Type	Error	UpdR	DatTyp	Prcsn
Cycle counter	Meas	BMS	I	< 1 %	1 / Cycle	Flt	16 bit
	<i>Notes:</i>						
Current	Meas	BMS	I	< 1 %	10 Hz	Flt	16 bit
	<i>Notes:</i>						
Cell impedance	Meas	BMS	I	$\pm 10 \mu\Omega / \pm 1^\circ$	FltArr	16 bit	
	<i>Notes:</i>						
Test data	Calc	Cloud	I	< 1 %	5% <i>SOH</i>	FltArr	16 bit
	<i>Notes:</i>						
Capacity	Calc	BMS	O	< ± 5 %		Flt	16 bit
	<i>Notes:</i>						
<i>RUL</i>	Calc	BMS	O	< ± 5 %		Flt	16 bit
	<i>Notes:</i>						

5.2 MSM

EIS driven MSM *NEMO_SYS_20701aee*

links outgoing: ,

The EIS driven MSM is needed to identify the mechanical state of a battery cell from electrical measurements provided by the BMS. *EIS* will be exploited in order to find frequencies sensitive to a mechanical state. A physics-based model will process the BMS input.

Objective:

- Estimate reversible and irreversible swelling of single battery cell
- Estimate mechanical load on single battery cell

EIS driven MSM - Model parameterization protocol *NEMO_SYS_9a0fa4ac*

- Experiment: Mechanical abuse test (0% *SOC*) to derive mechanical stiffness
- Calibration: Apply preload force and vary *SOC* to find correlation with *EIS*
- Validation: Single cell cycling with preload force and mapping of preload force and thickness (swelling) evolution

EIS driven MSM - Concept of distributed computing & computing time *NEMO_SYS_26249256*

- Estimated computing time: Low
- Low calculation resources needed, could run on Aurix
- Programming language: Python or Matlab
- Time criticality: non critical

EIS driven MSM - Model Input & Output *NEMO_SYS_c5bc904b*

Abbreviations used in the model overview table: Meas = Measured; Calc = Calculated; I = Input; O = Output; UpdR = Update rate; DatTyp = Data type; Flt = Float; FltArr = Float array; Prcsn = Precision; d = Day;

Parameter	Class	Source	Type	Error	UpdR	DatTyp	Prcsn
Cell voltage	Meas	BMS	I	± 3 mV	10 Hz	Flt	16 bit
Cell impedance	Meas	BMS	I	± 10 $\mu\Omega$ / $\pm 1^\circ$	0.1 Hz	FltArr	16 bit
	Notes: Same frequency as <i>EIS</i> under load;						
Module current	Meas	BMS	I	± 1 A	10 Hz	Flt	16 bit
<i>SOC</i>	Calc	Model	I	< 1 %		Flt	16 bit
	Notes:						
<i>SOH</i>	Calc	Model	I	< 1 %		Flt	16 bit
	Notes:						
<i>DRT</i>	Calc	Model	I			FltArr	16 bit
	Notes:						
Mechanical stiffness	Meas	Experiment	I	0 %	.	Flt	16 bit
	Notes: Stiffness of single battery cell						
Confinement stiffness	Meas	Experiment	I	0 %	.	Flt	16 bit
	Notes: Stiffness of confinement - settable parameter						
Electrode thickness	Meas	Experiment	I	0 %	.	Flt	16 bit
	Notes: Measured by VUB SURF						
Preload force	Calc	<i>MSM</i>	O	< ± 5 %	< 1 Hz	Flt	16 bit
	Notes: Accuracy will depend on system stiffness						
Swelling	Calc	<i>MSM</i>	O	< ± 5 %	< 1 Hz	Flt	16 bit
	Notes: Accuracy will depend on system stiffness and battery cell						

5.3 P-ECM

EIS driven P-ECM *NEMO_SYS_1c4f5264*

An *EIS* driven *P-ECM* shall be developed and parameterized. The *P-ECM* shall be used for *SOC*, *SOH*, and core cell temperature estimation.

EIS driven P-ECM - Model parameterization *NEMO_SYS_b0bfede1*

The *P-ECM* is parameterized by generating *EIS* data as a function of *SOC* and cell temperature within a predefined modelling grid, e.g. *SOC* in 5 % steps, temperature in 5 °C steps. The complex impedance data $Z(j\omega)$ is processed by *DRT* and R_{ohmic} and g_τ are retained as a function of *SOC* and cell temperature. The maxima of g_τ are determined and associated R_i and C_i values are determined, where τ determines C_i and the surface around the local maxima determines R_i . R_i and C_i depend on *SOC* and cell temperature. All *P-ECM* parameters, i.e. R_{ohmic} , R_i , and C_i , are interpolated with respect to *SOC* and cell temperature.

EIS driven P-ECM - Boundary Conditions *NEMO_SYS_93787558*

- temperature range: from -20°C to 50°C
- current/power range: according to cell specifications
- SOC range: from 0% to 100%
- SOH range: from 100% to 80%

EIS driven P-ECM - Model Input & Output *NEMO_SYS_a5f5ac2b*

Abbreviations used in the model overview table: Meas = Measured; Calc = Calculated; I = Input; O = Output; UpdR = Update rate; DatTyp = Data type; Flt = Float; FltArr = Float array; Prcsn = Precision; d = Day;

Parameter	Class	Source	Type	Error	UpdR	DatTyp	Prcsn
Cell voltage	Meas	BMS	I	± 3 mV	100 Hz	Flt	16 bit
Cell temperature	Meas	BMS	I	± 3 °C	1 Hz	Flt	8 bit
Cell impedance	Meas	BMS	I	± 10 $\mu\Omega$ / $\pm 1^\circ$	1 / d	FltArr	16 bit
				Notes: Excitation frequency: 20 mHz - 1 kHz; 6 / decade;			
Module current	Meas	BMS	I	± 1 A	100 Hz	Flt	16 bit
<i>P-ECM</i>	Calc		O		1 / d	FltArr	16 bit
				Notes: $R_{ohmic} + R_i + C_i$ with $i = 1$ to max. 7, e.g., array with max. values = 15; all values are stored as a function of <i>SOC</i> and temperature.			
<i>SOC</i>	Calc	BESTIMATOR	O		1 Hz	Flt	16 bit
				Notes: BESTIMATOR inputs: Cell voltage, cell temperature, cell impedance, module current, <i>P-ECM</i> ; BESTIMATOR can run locally or in the cloud;			
<i>SOH</i>	Calc	BESTIMATOR	O		1 / d	Flt	16 bit
				Notes: BESTIMATOR inputs: Cell voltage, cell temperature, cell impedance, module current, <i>P-ECM</i> , $Q_{nominal}$; BESTIMATOR can run locally or in the cloud;			
<i>SOP</i>	Calc	BESTIMATOR	O		1 / d	Flt	16 bit
				Notes: BESTIMATOR inputs: Cell voltage, cell temperature, cell impedance, module current, <i>P-ECM</i> , $P_{nominal}$; BESTIMATOR can run locally or in the cloud;			
SOH_{GNN}	Calc		O		1 / d	Flt	16 bit
				Notes: Inputs: Cell impedance, <i>P-ECM</i> ;			
SOP_{GNN}	Calc		O		1 / d	Flt	16 bit
				Notes: Inputs: Cell impedance, <i>P-ECM</i> , $P_{nominal}$;			
T_{core}	Calc		O		1 Hz	Flt	16 bit
				Notes: cell core temperature; Inputs: Cell temperature, cell impedance;			
$SOS_{T_{core}}$	Calc		O		1 Hz	Flt	16 bit
				Notes: Inputs: T_{core} , Cell temperature, cell impedance;			

5.4 RUL

Lifetime model/RUL *NEMO_SYS_a52b15cf*

The lifetime model is developed following two methodologies and in both cases, the generated dataset from NEMO_GA_T71 is used as the base. The dataset will include the following:

- Cycling stress factor variations such as *DOD*, *SOC* range, temperature, C-rates, impedances, Ah throughput or full equivalent cycles etc.
- Storage stress factor variations such as storage *SOC*, temperature, and time.
- Ageing outcome will be expressed as capacity fade.

The lifetime prediction including *RUL* estimation on cell level will consider the above list of ageing aspects. The data-driven and hybrid aging models will follow the below concepts.

Lifetime model/RUL - Data-driven ageing model *NEMO_SYS_a57fea57*

- An extensive ageing dataset consisting of stressed parameters will be pre-processed.
- The ageing understanding from experimental results and literature may enrich the data mining and selection more appropriate.
- Further sensitivity analysis could be made for parameterization sorting.
- Advanced algorithms will be developed and trained/tested from existing database.
- The prechecked model can be retrained with generated dataset. Model optimization/tuning with automatic data flow pipeline is to be established.
- The developed model can be tested by the reference test results identifying the prediction error.

Lifetime model/RUL - Hybrid ageing model *NEMO_SYS_47026c2b*

- This framework is a hybrid concept of merging the data-driven model and *EIS*-driven *P2D* model.
- The two developed models interconnections will be studied identifying the interrelated parameters like impedances etc.
- The frequency based ageing mechanism identification in connection to the available data would help development of a more reliable model.
- The adaptable blackbox model can integrate the physical equations (*EIS*-driven) for parameters tuning resulting in more accurate model.
- The developed hybrid model can be tested by the reference test results and the ageing mechanism can be validated with postmortem.

Lifetime model/RUL - Model Input & Output *NEMO_SYS_652de83a*

Abbreviations used in the model overview table: Meas = Measured; Calc = Calculated; I = Input; O = Output; UpdR = Update rate; DatTyp = Data type; Flt = Float; FltArr = Float array; Prcsn = Precision; d = Day;

Parameter	Class	Source	Type	Error	UpdR	Dat-Typ	Prcsn
Cycle counter	Meas	BMS	I	< 1 %	1 / Cycle	Flt	16 bit
	<i>Notes: FEC will be based on Ah throughput</i>						
Current	Meas	BMS	I	< 1 %	10 Hz	Flt	16 bit
	<i>Notes:</i>						
Cell impedance	Meas	BMS	I	$\pm 10 \mu\Omega / \pm 1^\circ$	FltArr	16 bit	
	<i>Notes:</i>						
Test data	Calc	Cloud	I	< 1 %	5% <i>SOH</i>	FltArr	16 bit
	<i>Notes:</i>						
Capacity	Calc	BMS	O	< ± 5 %	Flt	16 bit	
	<i>Notes:</i>						
<i>RUL</i>	Calc	BMS	O	< ± 5 %	Flt	16 bit	
	<i>Notes:</i>						

5.5 SOS

SOS estimator *NEMO_SYS_acfd9e24*

The state of safety estimator is needed to detect a safety-critical change to a battery cell and cell failure in the module. Its functionality is divided into a short-term prediction and a long-term estimation. The *SOS* estimator should increase the battery safety by an early failure detection.

Objectives:

- Short-term detection of cell failure
- Long-term safety estimation
- Tolerable load of the cell until cell failure occurs

SOS estimator - Concept *NEMO_SYS_bfcd165e*

Cell failure

- Abusive load (mechanical, thermal, electrical)
- Internal short circuit
- Thermal runaway
- Destructive tests with zBMS: *BMS* hardware might be destroyed by thermal runaway

Model parameterization protocol*

- Abuse tests
- Cycling with pre-damaged cells
- Algorithm development

Concept of distributed computing & computing time

- Estimated computing time: Low
- Low calculation resources needed, could run on Aurix
- Data storage must be external
- Time criticality: short time event (cell failure) within seconds

SOS estimator - Model Input & Output *NEMO_SYS_2951d1c1*

Abbreviations used in the model overview table: Meas = Measured; Calc = Calculated; I = Input; O = Output; UpdR = Update rate; DatTyp = Data type; Flt = Float; FltArr = Float array; Prcsn = Precision; d = Day;

Parameter	Class	Source	Type	Error	UpdR	DatTyp	Prcsn
Cell voltage	Meas	BMS	I	± 3 mV	10 Hz	Flt	16 bit
	Notes:						
Cell impedance	Meas	BMS	I	$\pm 10 \mu\Omega / \pm 1^\circ$	0.1 Hz	FltArr	16 bit
	Notes: Same frequency as <i>EIS</i> under load;						
Cell impedance	Meas	BMS	I	$\pm 10 \mu\Omega / \pm 1^\circ$	1 / Cycle	FltArr	16 bit
	Notes:						
Module current	Meas	BMS	I	± 1 A	10 Hz	Flt	16 bit
	Notes:						
<i>SOC</i>	Calc	Model	I	< 1 %		Flt	16 bit
	Notes:						
<i>SOH</i>	Calc	Model	I	< ± 5 %		Flt	16 bit
	Notes:						
<i>DRT</i>	Calc	Model	I			FltArr	16 bit
	Notes:						
Preload force	Calc	<i>MSM</i>	I	< ± 5 %	< 1 Hz	Flt	16 bit
	Notes:						

Parameter	Type	Source	Type	Error	UpdR	DatTyp	Prcsn
Swelling	Calc	<i>MSM</i>	I	< ± 5 %	< 1 Hz	Flt	16 bit
	Notes:						
<i>RUL</i>	Calc	Model	I	.		Flt	16 bit
	Notes:						
T_{core}	Calc	Model	I			Flt	16 bit
	Notes:						
T_{TR}	Meas	Experiment	I	0 %	.	Flt	16 bit
	Notes: Temperature for <i>TR</i>						
Critical deformation	Meas	Experiment	I	0 %	.	Flt	16 bit
	Notes: Deformation for <i>TR</i>						
dV_{TR}	Meas	Experiment	I	0 %	.	Flt	16 bit
	Notes: Voltage drop for <i>TR</i>						
Current <i>SOS</i>	Calc	<i>SoS</i> estimator	O	.	< 1 Hz	Flt	16 bit
	Notes: Short-term <i>SoS</i>						
Predicted <i>SOS</i>	Calc	<i>SoS</i> estimator	O	.		Flt	16 bit
	Notes: Long-term <i>SoS</i>						

5.6 IAV Standard

SOC *NEMO_SYS_10e9ad72*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_1860edf*

The IAV standard model shall calculate the *SOC* under consideration of current measurement. An update against *OCV* shall be done at the end of a full charge phase.

SOH - Capacity *NEMO_SYS_c15fd091*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_1860edf*

The IAV standard model shall calculate the capacity during charging under consideration of boundary conditions like environment, temperature or previous recovery phase.

SOH - Resistance *NEMO_SYS_480cf80c*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_1860edf*

The IAV standard model shall calculate the internal resistance continuously during active state under consideration of boundary conditions like voltage, current and temperature measurement as well as the *SOC*.

SOF - Currents *NEMO_SYS_1c9cf00e*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_1860edf*

The IAV standard model shall predict charge and discharge currents for the ongoing operating point under consideration of boundary conditions like environment, temperature or ageing:

- Prediction of maximum allowed continuous charge and discharge currents.
- Prediction of maximum allowed short term charge and discharge currents.
- Prediction of maximum allowed peak charge and discharge currents.
- Prediction of maximum allowed continuous charge and discharge currents without derating due to temperature limits.

SOF - Voltages *NEMO_SYS_6b288abb*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_18606edf*

The IAV standard model shall predict the voltage during charge and discharge for the ongoing operating point under consideration of boundary conditions like environment, temperature or ageing:

- Prediction of minimum allowed continuous charge and discharge voltage.
- Prediction of minimum allowed short term charge and discharge voltage.
- Prediction of minimum allowed peak charge and discharge voltage.

SOF - Capacity *NEMO_SYS_cd10f704*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_18606edf*

The IAV standard model shall calculate the maximum usable and maximum remaining capacity continuously under consideration of boundary conditions like environment, temperature or ageing.

SOF - Energy *NEMO_SYS_ed91f29a*

links outgoing: *NEMO_SYS_18606edf*

The IAV standard model shall calculate the maximum usable and maximum remaining energy content continuously under consideration of boundary conditions like environment, temperature or ageing.

GLOSSARY

AFE	Analog Front End
API	Application Programming Interface
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
BMS	Battery Management System
CAN	Controller Area Network
CC	Constant Current
CC-CV	Constant Current- Constant Voltage
CMC	Cell Measurement Controller
CMS	Cell Management System
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DOD	Depth Of Discharge
DRT	Distribution of Relaxation Times
DST	Dynamic Stress Testing
EIS	Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy
EVB	Electric Vehicle Battery
FEC	Full Equivalent Cycles

HEV	Hybrid Electric Vehicle
I2C	Inter Integrated Circuit
MAPE	Maximum Absolute Percentage Error
MSM	Mechanical Swelling Model
NEMO	NExt-generation MOdels for advanced battery electronics
NTC	Negative Temperature Coefficient
OCV	Open Circuit Voltage
P-ECM	Physical Equivalent Circuit Model
P2D	Pseudo Two Dimensional
PHEV	Plug-In Hybrid Electric Vehicle
RUL	Remaining Useful Life
SEI	Solid Electrolyte Interphase
SOC	State Of Charge
SOE	State Of Energy
SOF	State Of Function
SOH	State Of Health
SOP	State Of Power
SOS	State Of Safety
SOTA	State Of the Art
SOx	State Of x, summarize all kind of states like charge, health or energy
SPI	Serial Peripheral Interface
TR	Thermal Runaway
UART	Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter

WLTP

Worldwide Harmonized Light-Duty Vehicles Test Procedure

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